

Authorship + Nothingness

I. The Abyss of Thought

When does the author disappear other than through works? How can careerist and neo-utilitarian agendas be abandoned other than through the transfer of the moral rights of authors to works? And, what is this resultant “nothingness” embraced by authors in favor of works?

These three questions open on to the well-known “abyss of thought.” Far from the abandoning of thought by the author, the existential rites associated with answering these questions introduce the conversation one “I” (authorial presence) may have with another “I” (non-authorial presence). The pretext is that the split is the rite of passage for authors and for works, across a form of nothingness as escape route. The escape route is the abandoning of authorial privilege on the behalf of a form-of-life for works that opens up the possibility for an entirely new class of works (life-works) that cannot be detected in advance, or without entering upon such a transitional state, by authors and by works, for authors and for works.

Often troubled as the “transcendental exception” for works, and often reduced on behalf of authors by law to semi-legalist code and/or privilege by power, this status known as moral right has become, across centuries, the great excuse for the commodification of knowledge. Its double legalistic status as code underwriting copyright law and as insubstantial honor bestowed upon authors has, without notable exception, slowly devolved to the actual loss of moral rights by authors and by works. The long march of commodifying anything whatsoever that may be converted to marketable product by Capital has led, in turn, to a very different abyss than that confronted by authors faced with the responsibility for what is irreducibly moral in works – i.e., the presence of prior art and the assimilation of always already given antecedents that under the stresses of spectral commodity status become the foundation for the distressed libidinal excesses of market ideology and the pursuit of either wealth or celebrity. The promise of the exception has long been foreclosed. Its development, in the Enlightenment, has suffered the consequences of endless reification across a broad spectrum of de-instantiated measures associated with the so-called knowledge commons. That the author effectively has no choice today other than to embrace one or the other form of nothingness is utterly telling, especially given the fact that Capital has long run out of frontiers to mine and exploit other than the mind and the exploits of the mind and heart. That scholarship and art have fallen to law and power is the foremost event of late-Capitalist hegemony and its infiltration, by imposition of rules and laws, of what formerly was known as General Intellect. There is nothing much left at large in excess of these measures that Capital has not decided is not worth pursuing. What is left unattended to is, effectively, the wreckage – which is generally “re-socialized” according to the processes of abandonment associated with the exploitation and depletion of resources.

This summary judgment is the lived experience of any and all authors who have nothing to offer that machinic world of algorithmic malfeasance, or of those who refuse accommodation with the edicts required for the acquisition of wealth and privilege. The fact that many authors try and fail to meet the machinic edicts of late-Capital lies somewhere in-between these two versions of nothingness, whereas the resultant and always optional valorization of apparent failure may lead nonetheless toward that abyss of thought that might produce, after all, the long-sought antidote.

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II. Privileging of Works

The privileging of works over authorial presence through the transfer of moral rights to works may only be accomplished experimentally. It will be of no use to return to pre-copyright premises, when the ownership of works was based on the ontic substantiation of and for works. A review of the ravages of the capitalization of the knowledge commons will also do little to alleviate the damages wrought over centuries. What is required is a complete departure from the rules and laws of knowledge production under Capital; and what is obvious, for authors and for works, is that the premise of the life-work also hold the promise of escape from all forms of re-accommodation with law and power.

The moral rights of works, if produced across the life-work, will serve as exit strategy. If that process includes trial and error (and if trial often means “trial” by Capital and Law), the primary concern becomes the transitional state

denoted in contemporary scholarship as “Art + Law” – a confluence of streams that produces, by its merger of debauched resources, a productive field of inquiry best left unnamed.

“Art + Law” is also the locus for the development of forms-of-life for forms of artistic scholarship. They can only be developed as “new exception,” but without the attendant recourse to legalistic maneuvers associated with otherwise well-meaning measures previously encribed under the rubric of “common law” or “creative commons.” Both terms have effectively proven non-resistant to re-colonization and re-appropriation by late-Capital, with the former being a benign form of public domain and the latter echoing that disturbed prospectus through its attempt to categorize new exceptions to proprietary measures associated with the knowledge commons. Both terms also contain a remainder that preempts the very departure sought. Any concept of a commons that might prove as fertile field for the development of forms-of-life for life-works will also have to deal with the mere fact that most immaterial labor has, irreducibly, an internal battleground within it that plays out across the dialectic of ontic and de-ontic status and rights – i.e., the very ground that Capital exploits to carry out its marauding mission across works in pursuit of “rent.” This spectralization of import and intent is the secret minefield constructed to prevent escape from the field of exploitation. The parameters are constantly shifting, and it is the constant surveying of that mined and enclosed ground that most summaries conduct all the while claiming that they are also seeking a way out or a minesweeping operation on behalf of authors and (sometimes) works.

This “sometimes” signals the fact that the minesweeping operation (such as that conducted by neo-Marxist critique) includes the liberation of works, when it most often favors the liberation of subjects. Yet, as first step, such a counter-proposition has value, even if it does not progress to the liberation of works. What is mostly a hidden opportunity, within all such surveys and all such ground-clearing efforts, is the bestowing of subject status to works. The long tail of the long history of authorial presence and privilege, when transferred to works, might, if conducted across works such that works dictate terms, produce an actual escape route versus a clearing and return to grounds that have proven to be inherently re-colonizable by law and power. Indeed, much of that which passes as acts of liberation are actually acts of de-colonization to be followed by re-colonization by other means. These other means are generally reducible to ideological positions taken, on behalf of subjects by emergent forms of law and power – e.g., the history of revolution often is also the history of the imposition of new laws by the newly privileged, and always at the cost of subjects and works.

In terms of forms-of-life for life-works, it is insufficient to merely clear the ground. And it goes without saying that the imposition of new laws on behalf of new powers is merely a change of status versus a change of state. The elemental discord remains in place. That “taking-place” for law and power is the return of the theft nominally abrogated by the ground-clearing exercise. Any review of any historical or cultural moment past wherein such efforts served to end one form of exploitation only to install another would and should serve notice on authors and on works that there is something always amiss, and that there is something always missing when and if one form of colonization is replaced by another.

Academia and the art world, arguably, run the gamut of this perennial process of discord, recovery, re-boot, and re-colonization. Powers succeed powers, and new rules succeed old rules. Fashions displace fashions, and new fashions are assimilated to re-configure the brinksmanship of the operational logics. Careerism and privilege abound. The art world is perhaps the more dynamic of the two, though no less rife with the implicit discord of chronic fatigue followed by nominal revolt and incidental recovery. The history of the arts is the forced march of fashions, to the tune of markets. The implied universality of the university is the subjugation of subjects to the prevailing conventions and biases of the production of knowledge. Idiomatic in the extreme, both worlds nonetheless converged under late-Capital to produce the spectral market economy denoted “knowledge commons.” Any works within either world have little to no chance of staking any claim to the status of life-work. The life-work at play in both is the architecture of the apparatus. Assimilation to that apparatus is the entire rationale for permission to enter either world, for authors and for works. Yet somewhere amidst the wreckage of the very concept of life-work resides a new exception premised not so much on refusal but on the unhoped-for subjective renewal through works of a form-of-life for life-works that cancels capitalist hegemony once and for all.

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